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An Overview of Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches on the Synthesis of Heterocyclic Kojic Acid Scaffolds through the Multi-Component Reactions

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Abstract

Multi-component reactions as powerful synthetic methods were developed to provide efficient complex scaffolds, including kojic acid, through the one-pot one-step fashion. This review highlights the progress of multicomponent reactions covering kojic acid under different conditions through, short reaction time, higher yields, and environmental friendliness via producing various molecules. The aim of this paper is to review the literature from 2015 to 2020 via quantitative and qualitative approaches.

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